

CATEGORY – COMMUNITY, LIVELIHOOD

LANGUAGE – ENGLISH

Herding

Collaboration
and interaction

Multiple income
sources

Supplemental
feeding

Summer marking;
Calf marking

Calving in
enclosures

Gathering and
round-ups

Slaughtering

Pasture rotation

Production of
feed and hay

Leverage from
the EU
2014–2020

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 869471

CATEGORY – COMMUNITY, LIVELIHOOD

LANGUAGE – ENGLISH

Herders'
numbers, age,
part/full-time work

Herder wellbeing

Reindeer healthcare

Culture, values,
and traditions

Traditional
knowledge;
Education

Technology

Leverage from
the EU
2014–2020

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CATEGORY – CLIMATE, ENVIRONMENT

LANGUAGE – ENGLISH

Calving

Rut

Predator populations

Reindeer population and welfare

Spring weather;
Snow melt;
Vegetation growth

Summer weather;
Insects;
Mushrooms

Autumn weather;
Frosts;
Snow/ice cover

Winter weather;
Snow conditions

Leverage from
the EU
2014–2020

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CATEGORY – LAND USE

LANGUAGE – ENGLISH

Agriculture

Forestry

Gold digging

Mining

Peat production

Hydro power

Wind power

Infrastructure
and settlements

Second homes

Summer pastures

Leverage from
the EU
2014–2020

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CATEGORY – LAND USE

LANGUAGE – ENGLISH

Winter pastures

Protected and recreational areas

Hunting;
Dogs

Wildlife tourism
and baiting

Leverage from
the EU
2014–2020

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CATEGORY – SOCIETY, ECONOMY, GOVERNANCE

LANGUAGE – ENGLISH

Reputation and
image of livelihood

Reindeer
product brands

Indigenous rights

International
policy agreements

Land-use
planning

Meat markets

National
legislation

Profitability
and costs

Subsidies and
compensations

Trust
between actors

Leverage from
the EU
2014–2020

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CATEGORY – JOKERS, SURPRISES

LANGUAGE – ENGLISH

Climate change effects;
Extreme weather

Climate change mitigation;
Green transition

Pandemics and related restrictions

Geopolitical tensions

Leverage from
the EU
2014–2020

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